

**THE INFLUENCE OF INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS ON
LEARNING OF CELL BIOLOGY IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN
IKPOBA OKHA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF EDO STATE**

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JUNE, 2023

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**A RESEARCH PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF
CURRICULUM AND INSTRUCTIONAL TECHNOLOGY, FACULTY
OF EDUCATION, UNIVERSITY OF BENIN, BENIN CITY, EDO
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CERTIFICATION

We the underlined certify that this research work was carried out by **Jedidiah Simi OSEYI** in the department of Curriculum and Instructional Technology, Faculty of Education, University of Benin.

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DEDICATION

This project work is dedicated to God almighty who saw me through my undergraduate programme in the university of Benin, for the successful completion of this work and for granting me understanding, strength and speed to finish strong.

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At this point, I very much appreciate my project supervisor Dr. (Mrs.) O. O. Osawaru for her guidance, support, patience, and constructive criticism in the course of writing this project.

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Furthermore, I also want to acknowledge my lecturers in the Department of Curriculum and instructional technology for the knowledge acquired from them during my course of study in this institution, my profound gratitude also goes to my colleagues for their love and support.

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the influence of instructional materials on learning of Cell Biology in secondary schools in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area of Edo State. A research question and a hypothesis were raised to guide the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The sample population of the study was 150 Biology students' across selected secondary school in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area of Edo State. They were sampled using the simple random sampling technique. **The** instrument used in the study was a questionnaire titled "the influence of instructional materials on learning of Cell Biology in secondary schools". Data obtained from the instrument were analyzed using mean, simple percentage and T.Test. Findings from the study revealed that the use of instructional materials influences student's understanding of the concept of cell biology; that the use of instructional materials has no significant influence based on sex (either male or female); that the Government should provide good working Environment for teachers and necessary teaching equipment's important for student to learn Biology and that the teacher should recognize that Biological concepts can only be best taught to their learners via instructional materials. Recommendations were made based on the findings of the study; that Government should provide good working Environment in schools to foster better learning by students; that Government should employ more teachers who are technologically, and IT orientated; that teaching and learning activities should be compactable to the student mind, age and psychological development.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Background of the study

Biology is one of the science subjects offered at the senior secondary school levels in Nigerian Secondary Schools (NPE, 2004). Biology is a very important science subject and a requirement for higher learning in a number of science-related professional courses like medicine, agriculture, pharmacy.

Biology is a natural science that deals with both the living and non-living world: How the world is structured, how it functions and what these functions are, how it develops, how living things came into existence, and how they interact to one another and with their environment. It is a prerequisite subject for many fields of learning that contributes immensely to the technological growth of the nation. This includes medicines, pharmacy, nursing, agriculture, forestry, biotechnology, nanotechnology, and many other areas (Ahmed & Abimbola, 2011).

Cell Biology is an aspect of Biology science that is taught in school. Biology as a science subject is practical based. Therefore, to effectively implement the curriculum it requires that both the teachers and students should

extensively carry out many activities using modern, current, and suitable instructional materials. More so, cell Biology cannot be taught effectively without the use of appropriate instructional materials.

The influence of instructional materials in the cell Biology curriculum cannot be over emphasized. This is for the fact that such materials enhance, facilitate and make learning easy, lively and concrete.

Instructional materials is essential for effective behavior change in learners. According to Etukudo (2009), poor achievement in Biology is incontrovertibly attributed to poor instructional delivery approach adopted by teachers in schools.

Instructional materials are essential and significant tools needed for teaching and learning of school subjects to promote teachers 'efficiency and improve students' performance. They make learning more interesting, practical, realistic and appealing. They also enable both the teachers and students to participate actively and effectively in lesson sessions. They give room for acquisition of skills and knowledge and development of self- confidence and self-actualization. Some scholars defined teaching aids as those materials used for practical and demonstration in the class situation by students and teachers. Instructional materials as objects or devices that assist the teacher to present a

lesson to the learners in a logical and manner. Instructional materials are such used by teachers to aid explanations and make learning of subject matter understandable to students during teaching learning process.

Learning by doing was emphasized in the curriculum so that the students should be able to identify and produce basic Biological products for themselves and their community. A series of activities were suggested in the curriculum to ensure the development of psychomotor skills in Biology by the students. The curriculum further recommended that: each student be guaranteed adequate equipment, lab space, lab structures and regular supply of reagents and practical specimen. In addition student's achievement should be continuously assessed through various forms of classroom tests, fields and laboratory practical.

To support this assertion, many researchers have adduced that poor achievement in public examinations is traceable to instructional delivery approaches adopted by teachers. The resultant effect is the low achievement and low retention level in student's outcome both in internal and external examinations. This implies that the mastery of Biology concept might not be fully achieved without the use of a good instructional delivery approach that utilizes instructional materials. Research has noted that when the students are given the chance to learn through more senses than one, they can learn faster

and easier. Therefore, scholars referred to instructional materials as objects or devices which help the teacher make learning meaningful to the learner. They are materials used to aid the transferring of information from one person to another.

The students learn better when most of the senses are appealed to the instruction and use of instructional materials in Biology education has added a new dimension in the positive promotion of the teaching and learning process. It provides the much need sensory experiences needed by the learners for an effective and meaningful behavioural change. Instructional materials are meant to improve the quality of education for effective academic performance of agricultural science students in schools. The performance of the students on the intended learning outcome provide the validation – loop on the success of the interaction and instruction.

The influence of instructional materials in the teaching and learning of Biology and how instructional materials help student to easily and intelligibly comprehend the subject, is the focus of this study.

Statement of the problem

There is a general impression that science education is not achieving the desired objectives especially with high incidence of students' poor performance in Biology and other science subjects at senior secondary certificate examination. The deteriorating state of our educational system is quite worrisome.

The problem teachers and students encounter in our educational system include inadequate learning materials, the procurement of the instructional materials, the effective use of instructional materials in schools, lack of electricity supply to operate some visual aids, lack of qualified educational technologists to operate them and lots more. This situation has assumed a precarious dimension in all secondary schools in Edo State and particularly in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area. The failure of educational system to provide adequate and appropriate teaching-learning aids in order to improve academic performance of students is of a great concern to government, educational institutions and other concern citizens. It is believed that if adequate instructional materials are made available to school and are used appropriately in learning process, a better performance could be achieved.

Hence, this study seeks to find out the influence of instructional materials in the learning of Biology in senior secondary schools students.

Research questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the investigation:

1. What is the influence of instructional materials in the learning of Biology in secondary school?

Hypotheses

Ho: There are no significant difference in the influence of instructional materials in the teaching and learning of Biology based on sex.

Purpose Of The Study

The major purpose of the study is to determine the influence of instructional materials on learning of Cell Biology in secondary schools in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area of Edo State. In order to achieve this major purpose, certain specific purposes will be considered so investigations will be undertaken:

- To investigate the influence instructional materials has on the learning of Biology in secondary school.

Significance Of The Study

It is therefore the researcher's expectation that upon completion of this study, the findings will be beneficial to teachers, students, parents, government at all levels and the general public in many ways.

First, this study will assist the teachers in secondary school in Ikpoba Okha Local Government to adopt the consistent use of instructional materials in the classrooms to make teaching and learning interesting and enhance better understanding by the students especially in core subject areas.

More so, it is seen and believed that the use of instructional materials will immensely help in creating picture interaction in the mind of those that are slow to learn in the school learners.

Secondly, this study will be of benefit to parents and guardians of students it will help them to appreciate the importance of the use of the instructional materials to aid their children's understanding in all the subjects they are taught.

This will induce them to cooperate with the school authorities to provide all necessary instructional materials needed to be used in the senior secondary school classroom.

Thirdly, to the government, this study is also important at local, state, and the federal government level because it will help them to understand the place of instructional materials in terms of pedagogical practice. Secondary school in Ikpoba Okha Local Government to adopt the consistent use of instructional materials in the classrooms to make learning interesting and enhance better understanding by the students.

This research will also serve as a point of inquiry and reference for both students and members of the public who want to know or carryout related study on this area.

Scope and Delimitations Of The Study

This study dealt with the influence of instructional materials in the teaching and learning of Biology in secondary schools in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area of Edo State. The study scope deals with the influence of instructional materials in teaching and learning of Biology amongst students in secondary schools in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area of Edo State.

This research work is delimited to senior secondary one and two (SS1-SS2) in public and private schools in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area Edo State Nigeria.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The aim of this chapter is to present already existing views of people in related topic on “Influence of Instructional Materials in the teaching and learning of Cell Biology in Secondary Schools in Ikpoba Okha LGA, Edo state Nigeria.”

This chapter is sequentially arranged and discussed under the following sub-headings:

- The concept of instructional materials
- Forms of instructional materials
- Characteristics of instructional materials
- The Influence of Instructional Material on Teaching and Learning
- Importance and uses of instructional materials
- Factors guiding the selection of instructional materials
- The significance of instructional materials
- Problems Facing the Selection of Instructional Materials for Teaching and Learning cell Biology
- Summary review of Literature

Concept of instructional materials

Instructional Materials or instructional aids as the name suggests, are materials of visual, audio and audio - visual category that helps to make concepts abstracts and ideas concrete in the teaching/learning process. They are also materials which the teacher uses in supplementing his teachings. Instructional Materials include materials used to facilitate learning for better results. Hence, it is not just the use of tools of technology alone but a systematic, integrated organization of machines hard wares and soft wares and man, teachers etc, to the solution of problems in education.

In trying to conceptualize instructional materials we realized that different people from various fields of education have being able theatrically and practical state their opinions as to what instructional materials are. Some say that instructional materials are the tools used in educational lessons, which includes active learning and assessment while others propose that instructional material are resources a teacher uses to help him teach his students in an teaching/learning situation.

Instructional materials have been defined by various authors. For example, Oluwagbohunmi and Abdu-Raheem (2014) acknowledged that instructional materials are such used by teachers to aid explanations and make learning of

subject matter understandable to students during teaching learning process. Adeoye, (2012) defined instructional materials as items used to aid the transferring of information from one person to another. Therefore, Iherionwu (2000) referred to instructional materials as objects or devices which help the teacher make learning meaningful to the learner. Obanya viewed them as *didactic materials* things which are supposed to make learning and teaching possible.

It can also refer to all tools which can easily be used by a teacher to correct wrong impressions and to illustrate things that learners cannot forget easily (Ema & Ajayi 2004). Ikerionwu (Isola, 2010) referred to them as *objects or devices*, which help the teacher to make a lesson much clearer, (logically and sequentially) to the learner.

According to Abdullahi (1982), instructional materials are materials or tools locally made or imported that could make tremendous enhancement of lesson impact if intelligently used. Instructional materials are also described as *concrete or physical objects* which provide sound, visual or both to the sense organs during teaching (Agina-obu, 2005). “Instructional materials are any media which promotes perceptions, Understand transfer of knowledge and retention of ideas” (Ivork 1971). Agina-Obu (2005) submitted that instructional materials of all kinds appeal to the sense organs during teaching and learning. Ughamadu (1992) defined instructional materials as the resource that the teacher

and students use to influence the effectiveness of teaching and learning process. In his own perspective, Fadeiye (2005) saw instructional materials as visual and audio-visual aids, concrete or non-concrete, used by teachers to improve the quality of teaching and learning activities in sciences. Brunner (1956) says that, “instructional materials are what help the Students to realize their learning objective” instructional materials as acts of giving help normally by teachers to provide help and encouragement in students or pupils learning activities. Instructional materials refer to those alternative channels of communication, which a classroom teacher can use to concretize a concept during teaching and learning process. Traditionally, classroom teachers have relied heavily on the '*talkchalk*' method during their teaching. But recently, instructional materials help to provide variations in the ways in which messages are sent across. In using instructional materials teachers and students do not only extend the range of sense organs we use but also extend the range of materials used for conveying the same message through the same *organ*. For instance, in teaching a topic a teacher can manipulate real objects or use their stimulators. Instructional materials therefore constitute the media of exchange through which a message transaction is facilitated between a source and a receiver. In addition to extending the range of materials that can be used to convey the same instructional message to learners instructional materials also facilitate the 'process' nature of communication. In this passage, the process

nature of communication implies that both the source and the receiver of a message are actively involved in a communication encounter. Infarct, it means that both the receiver and the source share and exchange ideas, feelings in any communication (Tyler, 1987, Dike 1989)...

Examples of instructional materials are charts, maps, diagrams, comics, models, globes, slides, film strips, television, radio cassettes, video, recorders, cinema, public address system, laboratories and museums, flash Cards, flannel boards, card boards, Calendar, Computers, etc. Classification of Instructional Materials

Types Of Instructional Materials

The Instructional Materials could best be Classification in to three types:

Audio materials (deal with sound only) , Visual materials (as in sight) and Audio – visual materials (a combination of audio and visual i.e. sound and vision)

1. Audio materials (deal with sound only):

These include such things as Radio, Record players cassettes gramophone etc. These aid teaching through the sense of hearing. They can be used in teaching of specimen, Biological theories, and at the same time Biological concepts can be expertly presented via them.

- i.** **Radio:** This is audio kinds of media which could either uses battery or electric power in appealing to the sense of hearing. It is a media for communication and it is used in the process of delivering lesson such topic as communication in social studies as instructional materials for the pupils or students to perceive the concept in a practical manner.
- ii.** **Visual:** The category of this consist of maps, Film steps, specimen, pictures, charts, Blackboard, posters etc. This category appeals to the pupils through the sense of sight, the saying that seeing, is believing applies to some extent in this context. Until facts are presented in form of visual aid, pupils may not readily grasp the meaning of ideas, concepts and facts.

2. Films/film projectors: Ajayi (2004) describe films/film projectors are 16mm wide and are shown using a 16mm projector, some are designed to help teach facts and exact steps of procedure. Others are suitable for general orientation to a subject. Still others are effective in developing understanding of complex in societal historical problems and for influencing attitudes. Although, projecting educational films is not always the issue but the effective use of it to portray the ideas of the content of the lessons or topics in hand and the teacher process of

using it might be something else that the students would not be able to comprehend the factual information of the lesson taught using the materials.

3. **Audio-visual:** As have said already, this group consists of a combination of both audio and visual materials. They are therefore things like Television films and projector etc, the use of these aids learning greatly.

i **Video cassette/Video Disc machines:** These are essentially a television receiver minus or without a display tube. They have facilities for recording television and other video inputs and for playing back programmes recorded on video cassette. Ema (2006) state that, many machine have the ability to “freeze” the picture at a given frame, or to “slow motion” feature that have obvious advantages in educational situation. Since the media have the ability of freezing the picture at given frame, it then shows that it can be used to teach social studies students, different concrete issues at the students’ pase While, video disc is a disc on which visual objects, with or without are electronically recorded.

ii. **Tape recorders:** Tapes recorders are Medias used in an educational setting to play back pre-recorded audio lessons or activities to a class to provide illustrative audio materials in the context of ‘live’ lesson or activities. These could be either be bought or improvised by the teacher or recorded off-air. Ema and Ajayi (2004) argued that, recording have been used successfully in the

teaching of languages and laboratories on the handling of equipment. They expressed further that, “As with all other aids, the effective use of the tape recorder demands careful planning. Its real value derives from its ability to augment visual with audio stimuli. Use in a casual manner its impact declines while diminishing returns set in quickly”.

Classification Of The Forms Of Instructional Materials

Many educationists agree that instructional materials bring about improvement in the teaching learning process as well as permit teachers and students to interact as human beings these instructional materials are classified into three forms which are;

- Projected and electronic materials.
- Non-projected materials.
- Phenomenal and manipulative materials

(1). Projected And Electronic Materials

Projected and electronic materials are forms of media which could be visual, audio and audio-visual in nature that requires projection and electricity in their using process for teaching and learning situation. Emma & Ajayi (2004) categorized projected and electronic media into the following: film/film projectors, video cassette / video Disc machines, tape recorders/recordings;

radio, slide projectors, overhead transparencies/overhead projectors, opaque projectors (Episcope) and computer.

Slide/slide projector: A slide is a single positive image or transparent materials (a slide transparency) held in a mount and designed for projection (Ajayi 2006).

She further expressed that, if properly designed, slides can be of great assistance to a teacher in providing visual reinforcement for what he is saying, are particularly useful for showing photographs, diagrams and other graphic materials. Too-much information should not be included on a slide. Thus, an educational or social studies slide should be clear, simple, and capable of being seen and understood from all parts of the classroom in which it is being projected.

Overhead transparencies/overhead projectors: Ajayi & Ema (2004) the overhead projector (OHP) consists of a horizontal table (250 × 250m) on which the materials to be projected is placed. Light from the bulb below the table is condensed by a concave mirror or by a fresnellens, passes through the materials to be projected and is focused and turned through 90° by a lens system mounted on a stalk on bracket above the table. The material to be projected is usually a transparency. An overhead transparency is a transparent sheet of material

intended for use with an overhead projector as a means of showing graphic, textual and other information.

Opaque projector: This is a media that projects the image of solid objects on a screen by means of a light, which is concentrated on those objects and a mirror, which reflects the image through a lens. Solid materials or objects like models, pictures, maps charts, and graphs can be shown through opaque projector with clarity.

(2). Non-Projected Materials

Ughamadu (1992 in Anyanwu 2003) assert that, non-projected materials are these materials that do not require any form of projection before they can be used. Non-projected materials are different forms of instructional materials that required not the process of projection before its operation can take place. These could include the following, textual and non-textual, chalk-book, magnetic board/ soft/board flipchart, specimen, models etc.

Textual materials and non-textual materials refer respectively to all the print and non-print materials that are used by the teachers and learners for instructional process. The print materials are the textbooks, magazines, periodicals, journals, and newspapers, among others while the non-print materials includes. Charts, chalkboard, radio television, films videotapes, audiotapes, relia, festivals and

games (Esu 2004) expressed that together they assist the students in acquiring clear concepts of subject matter they are also students' best single academic friends. Moreover they can provide security for the unprepared teacher and an escape hatch for one who is instructing outside his field of specialization.

The textual print materials comprise so large a proportion of all teaching aids that selecting written materials for the teaching of a given unit poses specific problems the textual prints are the prescribed or main texts used for a given course. They are the set of books or course books specifically written for a given course or programme. There is a wide range of textual prints as well as supplementary ones as I have mentioned earlier.

While non-textual print materials are the print materials that supplement the main texts and enrich the learning situation. When combined with the correct use of the main text they can provide richness in learning experiences that can be gained in no other way. All these are durable materials that social studies should endeavour to explore and use during teaching and learning processes in order to enrich the concepts of social studies in the mind of the learners. Specimens are the real object or things a teacher can use for effective teaching of Cell Biology concepts. It makes social studies teachers' work easier and more participatory. These are objects like traditional wears, minerals, rocks,

plants etc. all these help the learners to see, touch, smell (where necessary) and handle physically which give them real natural experiences in learning. Textbooks are special types of books, which are written to satisfy a special need in the school curriculum (Ajayi and Emma 2005). They further classified textbooks into four categories; reference, general, course, and children textbooks. Adekeye (2008) identifies some criteria for selecting or writing textbooks in social studies, such as author, language age and vocabulary, content, format, does it reflect social studies objectives, are there any harmful ethnic-religious-gender or national bias, durability, availability, publisher data and many other relevant criteria were listed by her.

(3). Phenomenal And Manipulative Materials.

These instructional materials are majorly community based resources that promote the teaching-learning of social studies. Phenomenals are instructional situations such as events, things, features, settings, festivals and other community resources that are directly apprehended by the learner at their natural setting constitute this category (Esu 2004). They help to bring the learners in direct contact with learning experiences that far transcend volumes of recorded literature and weeks of sermonization. Despite the fact, of these positive ends, field trips and school journeys that normally bring learners into

contact with the phenomenals are underutilized because of time, finance, knowledge of the teacher, inflexibility of the school timetable and other infrastructural problems. Esu further asserts that, phenomenals can be natural or man-made. According to him, they include the following categories; community resources such as resource persons, museums, aquaria, zoos, farms, fish ponds, beaches, caves, hot springs, volcanic eruption sites, among others. He expressed further that, another groups includes dramatization, demonstrations, games, concerts, operas, dances and festivals. He equally encouraged that, social studies teachers should explore and widely utilize the phenomenals because these can stimulate aesthetic talents, promote, tactile stimulus and enhances identification and attachment not only with nature but also with the particular learning situation that they facilitate socialization process.

This class of instructional materials deals mostly with the affective but does not preclude the psychomotor and the cognitive domains he maintained.

Manipulative materials are instructional materials that, the learners actually handle skillfully, deal with, and manage expertly to bring about the desired behavioural changes. They are important for the development of skill in professional training (Esu 2004). They promote complete mastery of the content materials and the specific objectives. They also form part of both the

instructional and performance evaluation. The greatest significant of these materials is that, without them (or their upraised) neither the required leaning nor objectives evaluation can be adhered. Manipulative expresses the channel through which the required learning takes place. They cut across all aspects of skills development and mastery learning. These materials are vital for social studies because such skills as communication, tolerance, patience, and assertiveness are easily demonstrated, leant and observed through instructional games. Teaching of social studies can encourage some card and board games that have specific instructional values in order to enhance basic and logic reasoning amongst learners.

The Influence Of Instructional Material On Teaching And Learning

Fuller and Clark (1994) suggested that the quality of instructional processes experienced by a learner determines quality of education. In their view they suggest that quality instructional materials create into the learner's quality learning experience. Mwiria (1995) also supports that students performance is affected by the quality and quantity of teaching and learning resources. This implies that the schools that possess adequate teaching and learning materials such as textbooks, charts, pictures, real objects for students to see, hear and

experiment with, stand a better chance of performing well in examination than poorly equipped ones.

To Jimoh (2004), to teach is to show how to do something, to give lessons to a student or a group of students, to hold classes, to provide with knowledge and insight; the aim of teaching, Jimoh maintains further is to “equip students to learn how to learn and to teach them how to think”. In essence, the goal of teaching is learning.

For instance, Momoh (Isola, 2010), conducted a research on the effects of instructional resources on students’ performance in West Africa School Certificate Examinations (WASCE) in Kwara State. He correlated material resources with academic achievements of students in ten subjects. Data were collected from the subject teachers in relation to the resources employed in the teaching. The achievements of students in WASCE for the past five years were related to the resources available for teaching each of the subjects.

In an action research by investigators in Winneba District, a survey sample of teachers with several years of teaching experience of between (03) and twenty-five (25) years, claim that learning aids improve methodology. They also claim that learning aids reduce their talk and chalk method. The population comprised

teachers that were teaching in both urban and rural areas of Winneba. Eighty (80) teachers, male and female that were teaching in basic primary and secondary schools between March and April 1999 in Winneba District were subject of study.

They were teaching in twenty different basic primary and secondary schools. The eighty (80) selected subjects that responded to the questionnaire correctly have taught their subject disciplines which comprise Arts, Social Sciences and Physical science (including Biology) for between one and fifteen years and above. Each of the selected teachers teach as many as ten students to about fifty one to seventy in a class at a time. An on the spot evaluation of types of instructional materials they used, the quality and relevance to the topic taught were assessed by the investigators.

One of the slightly related articles was that of Uduma (1972) in which she Surveyed the biology teaching equipment in Enugu and Nsukka divisions and came out with conclusion that the schools investigated had up to half of the equipment required for the teaching-learning process of cell Biology at secondary school level.

In his study Adeogun (2001) revealed a strong positive link between instructional resources and academic performance of students in the process of teaching/learning. According to Adeogun, schools that possess more instructional resources performed better than schools that have less instructional resources. This finding supported the study by Babayomi (1999) that private schools performed better than public schools because of the availability and adequacy of teaching and learning resources. Adeogun (2001) noted that there was a low level of instructional resources available in public schools and hence commented that public schools had acute shortages of both teaching and learning resources. He further commented that effective teaching and learning cannot occur in the classroom environment if essential instructional resources are not available.

A study by Chonjo (1994) on the physical facilities and teaching learning materials in Primary schools in Tanzania supports the above views. Chonjo interviewed teachers and students on the role of instructional materials on effective learning. From his study he learned that performance could be attributed to adequate teaching and learning materials and equipments that are in a school. He recommended that in order to provide quality education the availability of sufficient quality facilities is very important. Chonjo's study was

one of its kinds in Tanzania which directly linked the role of physical facilities with students' academic performance in primary schools.

However, Chonjo focused only on physical facilities, leaving out instructional materials. To me, physical facilities such as buildings including classrooms, chairs and desks are not enough to provide quality teaching and learning. Instructional materials are also necessary. The study done by Maundu (1987) agrees with my ideas that, in order for a school to have a good performance it must be well equipped with relevant and adequate text books and other teaching and learning resources.

Qualities of an instructional materials

Odukwe, (1983) saw learning materials as essential part of practical teachings as such, in classrooms, pictures, charts and drawings should also be clear and neat. Odukwe added that, it is not good for a teacher to plan a lesson without some ideas of how he/she will stimulate or motivate his/her students by using pictorials illustrations (pictures, diagrams and apparatus) or materials illustrations. Olaitan, (1984) stressed that graphic materials to be used in classroom should be simple, attractive, large enough and not to be crowded with illustrations and colours. Ogundele, (1987) pointed out that good teaching aids

must have the following characteristics. This is because, the importance of any instructional materials lies in its ability to:

- Appeal to the senses (sound and sight)
- Attract and hold attention

Focus attention on essential elements to be learned at the proper time. In order to achieve the above objectives, any materials to be used as teaching aids must satisfied the following qualities:

- Flexibility: In the college or university, the teacher has been taught different ways of teaching hence, while in the classroom a good agricultural science teacher will attempt to teach his/her lesson using a variety of methods and materials. He/she should therefore, select or construct teaching aids that can be instantly modified to suit change in the approaches to construction.
- Colour: Since pupils are attracted by bright colours, these should be used in the preparation of teaching also however, too much brightness should be avoided since it may distract students intention from the objectives of the lesson and the instructional materials.
- Simplicity: Teaching aids must be simple and present only a far ideas at a time. This is because, students cannot comprehend complex ideas

presented to them at a shorttime. If pictures are used, they should illustrate only a very far words or actions. If more detailed pictures are used, student will not know that they are to notice.

- **Visibility:** All the smallest detailed to be used in an instructional materials, should be large enough to be seen by every student in the class. So, such should be placed conspicuously in front of the class to present a clear view to every student.

Anyawu (1989) added that the quality of good teaching aids can be seen under the followings:

- **Sufficiency:** Teaching aids must be sufficient enough for use.
- **Writing and Lettering:** The Lettering or writing must be bold, clear, neat and readable.
- **Attraction:** That the aids must be neat and attractive to arouse the interest of students. All the lettering must be bold and attractive.
- **Purpose:** The information in the aids must help the students in learning and must be relevant to the lesson.
- **Accuracy:** They must be accurate in content and language. There should be no mistakes of facts or spelling, that is, misinformation.

- Clarity: All details in the aids e.g. drawings, pictures etc., should be easily seen by the students farther away from it. Aids such as radio, tape and television should be clear enough to be heard by all students.

According to Farrant (1980), the quality of instructional materials (teaching aids) may be grouped into nine (9) categories – A, B, C as follows:

- Accurate – Information presented on every visuals should be up to date in every aspect.
- Appropriate: The visual aids for use, should be relevant to the topic as well as to learners. Visual aids should be used at the exact time when they will convey the right meaning they intend to convey.
- Artistic: Pictorial information should be realistically produced to the extent that it will make the same meaning of impression to every learner. It should be well produced.
- Bold: Information should be boldly presented so that the viewers or learners can see them clearly. Small pictures may not be visible from the back of the large class.

- **Brief:** Only essential information need to be inserted in the visual aids to avoid over crowdedness and irrelevance. As a rule main ideas should be few and stand out clearly for effective communication.
- **Bright:** Bright vision may brighten the learner view of contents while dull ones may cause a dull effect that may lead them to dozing off.
- **Clear:** The visual aid for use, should be clear so that every learner or viewer can quickly grasp its content. “A clustered chart is a confusing chart, if there is a lot of information to convey, develop a series of simple chart, rather than a single complex one” (Abdullahi, 1985).
- **Clean:** A dirty work is unattractive and put off learners. Visuals should be clean and well cared for to avoid damages.
- **Carefully Handled or Finished:** The planning and production of teaching aids, should be carefully carried out to give a deserved impression of good visual. Finally, a good teaching aid will provide adequate interaction.

Importance & Uses Of Instructional Materials

Many researcher and authority have comment immensely in the influence of instructional materials in Cell Biology instructions and any other educational processes, that the use cannot be over-emphasized. Abujaber (1987) assert that, the importance of instructional materials for both teacher and students cannot be over emphasized. In Cell Biology, the use of instructional materials is essential to support learning because social studies are concerned about natural and social phenomenal which cannot be easily expressed without the support of graphics maps, video, pictures etc. Cursor (1997) points out that using instructional materials in social studies classroom widens the channels of communication between teachers and their students. He further maintain that the instructional materials allow the growth of specific learning abilities and enhance intellectual skills and major skills-the use of charts and models enables the teacher to present and illustrate many physical phenomena and issues easily and at the same time, allows them to focus attention on the characteristic of objects.

Adeyanju (1997) Learning can be reinforced with learning aids of different variety because they stimulate, motivate, as well as arrest learners' attention for a while during the instructional process. In a research conducted by Adeyanju in university of winneba Ghana, a survey sample of teachers with several years of

teaching experiences of between (03) and twenty-five (25) years, claim that teaching aids improve methodology. They also claim that learning aids reduce their talk and chalk method while some of the teachers claim that whenever they taught with some of the instructional materials, their student get more stimulated because the learning aid help them (students) to become more attentive. In addition, students positive attitude generate more interest for the lesson they teach as a result students participate better in class activity Bozimo (2002) “the influence of instructional materials lies on the fact that abstract ideas, data or information expressed in printed pages become tangible and concrete when they are translated or reflected in forms of instructional materials and resource. she further maintain that, the inter disciplinary or integrated nature of Cell Biology demands that well thought-out materials be used in the classroom instructional to enable the learners comprehend the interrelatedness of knowledge and unity of various disciplines making up the Biology and humanities. The materials will also be such that can unambiguously reveal the dynamic nature of man, his activities, decisions and problems”.

We need to realize that, the application of instructional in Cell Biology classroom and any other instructional setting improves teaching-learning and allows the teachers and students to interact as human beings in the environment

they find themselves, for their own purpose. More specifically, instructional materials is use to concretize conceptual invisible realities in Cell Biology science, since the focal point of cell Biology is to instill in students practical skills that they will use to explore solution to their situational problems within the environment they live in.

Form the foregoing, the importance and the usefulness of instructional materials in Cell Biology science instructions can be best explain on the following points:

(1) Stimulation of interest.

In teaching-learning process, there is the need to generate, arouse, motivate and maintain students' interest. If the learners' interest is build properly, learning can take place effectively. As instructional materials have the potentials if effectively used for regulating the pace of information flow among different class of learners under the same classroom. It addresses individual differences and preserve-infact, Students are arouse with the nature and the beautiful appearance of the materials which will make them to Settle down and learn what the teacher had prepared to teach. Nnyejmesi (1981) sited by Anyawu (2003) agreed and based on investigations that pictures-i stimulates and help further study, helps children to take active interest in the topic presented, ii-

Manning admitted that they find pictures interesting and that pictures gave them clear ideas of the topic. This resulted in further activities and comprehension of the verbal materials.

(2). concretize abstract issues or topics in Cell Biology science.

The use of instructional materials in Cell Biology makes learning real, practical and more permanent to the learners. It makes conceptual abstraction in social studies more meaningful.

Esu (2004) states that; instructional materials are valuable assets in learning situations because they make lessons practical and realistic. They are the pivots on which the wheels of the teaching-learning process rotate. Since it concretizes issues, it then facilitates revision (recall) activities and provides very unique opportunities for self and group evaluation for the teacher and the students alike. It captures the student's intellect and eliminates boredom; makes the work easier, neater, boosting for clarity and more appealing.

3. Creating effective communication

Instructional materials if properly used allow for a flow and transmission of ideas from the teacher to the students and likewise from the students to the teacher or from one group to another.

The learners will be able to see, touch, spell what is been talked about by the teacher and be curious to ask questions that would be very helpful for effective evaluation (formative) of the teacher and instructions in Cell Biology.

(4). use for mass instructional and taking care of a wide audience.

With the use of projected and electronic materials such as television, overhead transparencies and computer especially, instructions are packaged in a very broad manners and which take care of wide range of learner in a classroom with less stress and time. Many students will be able to learn faster as the package takes care of various learners' interest at the same time. Teacher can handle a very large class conveniently as the teacher is guiding and displaying the instructional materials on the wall with the use of projector.

(5). providing meaning and useful sources of information to teachers and learners: Teachers are up to date and able to provide for reliable and useful information for the learners with the use of instructional materials, it can effectively be used to ultimate, shorten information from various sources for the purpose of comparison and contrasting ideas. It helps in perception and retention of information or knowledge in social studies learners.

(6). they help in developing a continuity of reasoning and coherence of thought: Biology science discipline been an integrate course of study that incorporate ideas from different disciplines, the use of instructional materials helps the learners on providing integrated experiences, which may vary from, disciplines which make the end product of education more productive. Since students are expose to the real nature of those concept or body of knowledge they tend to analyses and synthesis those body of knowledge for the proper application in their daily lives.

(7). the save time and reduce verbalism or repletion of words:

Emma & Ajayi (2004) asserts that “figurative speaking instructional materials enable the teacher to be in more than one place at a time and to address several issues at a time. For example, a video material could be on while the teacher moves around to explain to individuals students the subject contents in response to requests based on individual differences on problems. While the video material continues, providing details of the assignment the teacher also becomes part of the listening audience. It reduces verbalism or repetition of world by the teacher without knowing their meaning and also adds Varity in reinforcing verbal messages by providing a multimedia approach. Esu (2004) asserts that instructional materials are indispensable factor in a teaching learning process.

This is because or clearly words or verbalization has been found to be inadequate for effective teaching. Instructional materials, frankly speaking reduce the level at which the teacher should strives himself in the process of talking rather he guide the process of the instructions. And as a result save his time in process of teaching.

(8). they are use to perfect teaching methods and promote closer relations between the community and school:

The teachers of Biology perfect not only their methods of teaching but also perfect contents and situations (activities) to be taught. With the use of instructional materials, the teacher is able to edit, try and retry, alter and delete his activities to fit the standard of the students and also to effectively address the curriculum objectives.

Factors Guiding The Selection Of Instructional Materials

The teacher who wants to use instructional materials should consider the following variables to guide him in the selection of the types to be used in the teaching learning exercise.

- **Availability:** The Cell Biology teacher should ensure that the instructional materials to be used are easily available for use before the date of use. It means that the materials should be in store and the teacher

should look at it and test it before the day of the lesson. If the teacher has to prepare it himself, he should do so at least a day before the lesson. No instructional materials that are not available or not easy to prepare should be noted by the teacher in his lesson plan.

- **Accessibility:** It is the duty of the Cell Biology teacher to ensure that the materials to be used as instructional materials are not only available but also accessible to him. If they are already made materials they should be within reach of the teacher on the date and time of use. There should be no excuse that the materials are readily available but locked up in the store because the store-keeper is no-where to be found or the keys to the store have been misplaced.
- **Affordability:** The instructional materials to be used should not be expensive the cost should be such that either the teacher or the school can afford. It is no use to say that something is available but not affordable due to high cost. There should be a budget for instructional materials and when this is done the cost should not be outrageous it should be within the budget of the school.
- **Suitability:** The Cell Biology teacher using the instructional materials should ensure the appropriateness of the materials for his intended

learners. The materials should be suitable for their age, experience and intelligence. The legal, safety and ethical aspects of the materials to be used should equally be considered. The materials should not portray any anti-social attitude. They should also be free from any bias, distortion or prejudice. If the materials would need electric power then an alternative should be sought to avoid disappointment from Electricity.

- **Simplicity:** The instructional materials to be used should be simple to operate or manipulate. The teacher should test the materials and ensure their workability before the actual date of use. There should not be any technical problem and where electricity is to be used provision should be made for an alternative power. No teacher should use electric failure as an excuse for non-performance. In a situation where an instrument demands the hands of a technician, he (the technician) should be on hand and the teacher should have an insight into the operation of the instructional materials.
- **Qualitative:** The instructional materials selected for teaching by the teacher should be of good quality. Teachers should avoid the idea of "managing" with poor quality materials because he might not achieve the desired aim.

- **Regency:** The instructional materials should be the best or nearest to the best it should not be out of date. The instructional materials should reflect current and original thought.
- **Reliability:** As much as possible, teachers should make sure that the Instructional Materials so selected can be used to achieve the objective of the particular lesson. It is wrong for a teacher teaching pilgrimage to come into the class with an apparatus required to teach ablution. In this case, the Instructional Materials cannot be relied upon to achieve the objective of the lesson.
- **Relevance:** Care must be taken to ensure that only Instructional Materials that relate to the topic are used while teaching.
- **Cost:** The Instructional Materials should be within the reach of the teacher or the school. The cost of the Instructional Materials will determine whether it can be bought and used or not; otherwise the teacher selects only that Instructional Materials that costs less. In an event of the inability of the school and Age limit. It is wrong to bring into the class Instructional Materials that cannot be easily used to convey meaning of facts, ideas and concept to the pupils because of the limit of the pupils. A primary one school child may not be interested in a lesson in which

telescope is used to present facts. This means teaching Instructional Materials are not just selected on the basis of their attractiveness but on the basis of certain criteria that will ensure their effectiveness in the teaching and learning processes.

Problems Facing The Selection Of Instructional Materials For Teaching And Learning Cell Biology

In spite of the advantages of instructional materials, there are problems confronting their selection in Cell Biology. Balogun (2002) identified two main constraints militating against the successful improvisation of Science equipment. Among these problems are

1. **Lack of Fund:** There is no adequate support or patronage from the government and school administrators to encourage teachers of cell Biology in preparing instructional materials/resources. Some of the materials are very expensive to provide by teachers. For example, projected, electronic mass media and media that are retaining permanent knowledge to the students

2. **Teacher's Attitude:** Many of the school teachers are ignorant of using those instructional materials and induction course, lecture: and seminars are not organized in teaching profession as they are organized in the civil services to up-grade knowledge and to facilitate the use of sophisticated instructional

materials. Teachers also do not make maximum use of the few instructional materials at their disposal, because many of them do not have the knowledge of operating them.

3. Learner's Attitude: Many learners are not interested in choosing cell Biology as a Career, hence, they are ashamed and feel unconcern in supporting the teachers in the necessary training on the use and preparation of instructional materials. Also, the stealing of those instructional materials and problem of the students mishandling those instructional materials while teachers are not in the classroom, there is the problem of not leaving the instructional materials in the classroom, so that student can make use of them at their leisure and convenient time

4. Lack of facilities: Like resource room, masjid - prostration room and library. Many schools have no good building to store materials' for safety and on the part of those who have neglect cell Biology and held the belief that it is not essential part of its teachings.

5. Lack of adequate professional training: Maduabunmi (2003) reported lack of adequate professional training as a major problem militating against the effective use of local resources for Science teaching

Summary Of Literature Review And Uniqueness Of The Study.

This chapter discussed on the area other research had covered as regarding the reach topic. The chapter focuses on the concept instructional materials, The concept of instructional materials, Forms of instructional materials, Characteristics of instructional materials, The Influence of Instructional Material on Teaching and Learning, Importance and uses of instructional materials, Factors guiding the selection of instructional materials, The significance of instructional materials and Problems Facing the Selection of Instructional Materials for Teaching and Learning Cell Biology. Thus, this study examined “influence of Instructional Materials on The Teaching and learning of Cell Biology in Benin Ikpoba Okhra LGA”.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

In this chapter the methods adopted in carrying out the research study are described under the following sub-headings:

Research Design

Population of the study

Sample and Sampling Technique

Research Instrument

Validation of Instrument

Reliability of instrument

Administration of Instrument

Method of Data Analysis

Research Design of the Study

The design used was a descriptive survey design which includes the use of questionnaire. This method involves the collection of extensive data for the purpose of analyzing, describing and interpreting the questions raised on the

influence of instructional materials on teaching and learning of Biology in secondary schools in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area of Edo State.

Population of the study

The target population consists of 13330 students in the secondary schools across Ikpoba okha local government area of Edo State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Simple random sample technique was used to select the respondents a total number one hundred and fifty (150) which is about 1.2% of the population of the respondents in the Ikpoba okhra local government area of Edo State.

Research Instrument

The instrument used for data collection for the study was questionnaire. A closed ended questionnaire was designed based on the stated research questions. The questions contains thirteen item and was group into two sections; section, A and B respectively. Section A shows demographic data (personal data) characteristics, while sections B shows the research questions which consist of about 12 items on the research problem, and section C shows a check list of the items available.

Validity of the Instrument

The validity of the questionnaire (instrument) was determined, by the researchers project supervisor and two other lecture's from the Department of Curriculum and Instructional Technology, Faculty of Education, University of Benin who helped to scrutinize it and made necessary corrections. Thereafter, the corrections were effected.

Reliability of Instrument

In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, it was administered to 20 respondents, who were not part of the sample but part of the population. The Interrater reliability was calculated and the reliability coefficient was found to be 0.7 which is an indication that the instrument is reliable for the research.

Administration of Instrument

The instrument was administered by researcher to the various respondents, the items on the questionnaire were carefully explained to them by the researcher, who stayed back to give assistance to respondents who has some difficulty. The questionnaires were collected as soon as they were completed.

Method of Data Analysis

All tools for data analysis employed in the analysis of data of the data were descriptive and inferential statistic tool. The descriptive statistic tools percentage count, frequency count and mean

CHAPTER FOUR

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This chapter contains analysis, presentation of data and discussion of data generated from the study.

Presentation of Results

Research Question one: What is the influence of instructional materials in the learning of Biology in secondary school?

Table 4.1: the influence of instructional materials in the learning of Biology in secondary school

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	S	Mean	St.d	Decision
1	Students always have a better understanding of Cell Biology concepts anytime pictograms are used in the class	51	36	45	18	2.8	2.47	accepted
2	I understand cell Biology very well when Charts are used in classroom	45	36	60	9	2.78	2.429	accepted
3	I appreciate cell biology better when projector are used	27	43	38	42	2.37	2.056	Rejected
4	I find the Cell biology more interesting and understanding when Computer animations are used	6	45	72	27	2.2	1.78	Rejected
5	I like cell biology when Graphs are employed in learning	6	55	49	40	2.18	1.79	Rejected
6	Cell biology becomes interesting when Posters are used in the classroom	37	45	39	29	2.6	2.28	accepted

7	I understand cell Biology concepts when models of plant cells are used	46	23	51	30	2.57	2.28	accepted
8	I understand cell Biology concepts when models of animal cells are used	33	51	48	18	2.66	2.31	accepted
9	I learn cell Biology better with digital computer simulators (DCS).	48	35	39	28	2.69	2.4	accepted
10	I understand cell Biology better with use of Microscope	55	48	31	16	2.95	2.6	accepted
GRAND MEAN						2.58	2.24	

Results as presented in Table 4.1 indicate that all the ten(10) items relating to “the influence of instructional materials in the learning of Biology in secondary school” had an average mean rating of 2.58 ± 2.2 which exceed the theoretical mean of 2.50. Which implies majority of the respondent agreed that the use of instructional material cell biology influence their learning of the subject.

Majority of the respondents agreed that “the use of microscope help student to understand cell Biology better” 3.0 ± 2.6 , while minority of the respondents agreed that “Graphs employed in learning increase their interest for cell biology” 2.18 ± 1.79 .

Form the result above item 3, 4 and 5 were rejected. Item 1, 2, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 were accepted.

Other results for the above table shows in item 2 the respondents agreed that they understand cell biology very well when charts are used in classrooms 2.78 ± 2.43 .

Results from item 4 shows that, they find the Cell biology more interesting and understanding when Computer animations are used 2.2 ± 1.78 .

Results from item 6 show that, Cell biology becomes interesting when Posters are used in the classroom 2.60 ± 2.28 .

Results from item 7 show that, they respondents understand cell Biology concepts when models of plant cells are used 2.60 ± 2.28 .

Results from item 8 shows that, they understand cell Biology concepts when models of animal cells are used 2.66 ± 2.31 .

Results from item 9 shows that, I learn cell Biology better with digital computer simulators (DCS) 2.69 ± 2.31 .

Hypothesis one: What extents do students' perception of gender education as influencing adolescent reproductive health differs by gender?

TABLE 4:2 Gender

Items	Variables	Frequency N= 150	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	66	44
	Female	84	56
	Total	150	100

The results above shows that majority of the respondents are female with about 56% (84) of the population, while minority of the respondents are males with about 44% (66).

Table 4.2a : show the responds of the respondent based on gender

Independent variable	Mean (\bar{x})	sd	N	Alpha	T.Test
Male	2.60	2.30	66	0.05	0.49032873
Female	2.601	2.31	84		

Note: since the value of T is greater than value of $\alpha = >.05$

Therefore there is no significant difference between the opinion of female and male as regards sex.

The results from the table above show the response of the respondent base on gender, the results clearly shows that both male and female response (2.60 ± 2.30) and (2.60 ± 2.31) respectively this exceeds the theoretical mean of 2.50 which is the bench mark for this study. This implies that general the both sex agrees that instruction material improve their learning of cell biology in class.

Results from table 4.3a shows that there is no significant difference bases on sex as regard the use of instructional material in learning of cell biology.

Discussion of Findings

Results as presented in Table 4.2 indicate that all the ten(10) items relating to “the influence of instructional materials in the learning of cell Biology in secondary school” had an average mean rating of 2.58 ± 2.2 which exceed the theoretical mean of 2.50. Which implies majority of the respondent agreed that the use of instructional material cell biology influence their learning of the subject. Form the result above item 1, 2, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 where accepted Item 3, 4 and 5 where rejected.

Majority of the respondents agreed that “the use of microscope help student to understand cell Biology better” 3.0 ± 2.6 , while minority of the respondents agreed that “Graphs employed in learning increase their interest for cell biology” 2.18 ± 1.79 . This study is in line with the research conducted by Adesola, *et al.* (2022), who carried out research on the effect of instructional materials on Biology instructions among high achieving secondary school students in SPED international secondary school, Oyo, Nigeria, who reported that a lot of student preferred biology better when instructional material was employed for it learning activities. The results from the table above show the response of the respondent base on gender, the results clearly shows that both male and female response (2.60 ± 2.30) and (2.60 ± 2.31) respectively this

exceeds the theoretical mean of 2.50 which is the bench mark for this study. This implies that general the both sex agrees that instruction material improve their learning of cell biology in class.

Results from table 4.3a shows that there is no significant difference bases on sex as regard the use of instructional material in learning of cell biology.

This study is not in line with the research carried out by Yeo, *et al.* (2022) who undergo a study on the Impact of gender and prior knowledge on learning performance and motivation in a digital game-based learning biology course in Taiwan. He under study about 114 participates for this study. A quantitative research method was used to examine the impact of gender and prior knowledge on students' learning performance and motivation. In-depth interviews were conducted to explore the reasons for these impacts. The results showed that the improvement in the learning performance of females was significantly better than that of males.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter gives summary, conclusion and recommendation as regarding this research, below gives a detailed explanation of the above headings:

Summary

The study examined the influence of instructional materials on learning of Cell Biology in secondary schools in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area, of Edo State. One research question was raised with ten (10) items to guide the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The study used simple random sampling techniques to select respondents. The researcher designed a questionnaire which was used to gather for the study. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as of frequency counts, mean standard deviation and percentages.

The findings are as follows:

1. Results showed that all the ten (10) items relating to “the influence of instructional materials in the learning of Biology in secondary school” had an average mean rating of 2.58 ± 2.2 , which implies majority of the respondent agreed that the use of instructional material cell biology influence their learning of the subject.

2. Results showed that Majority of the respondents agreed that “the use of microscope help student to understand cell Biology better” 3.0 ± 2.6 ,
3. Results showed that minority of the respondents agreed that “Graphs employed in learning increase their interest for cell biology” 2.18 ± 1.79 .
4. Results showed that item 3, 4 and 5 were rejected. Item 1, 2, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 were accepted.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study the following conclusion was made on the influence of instructional materials on learning of Cell Biology in secondary schools in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area of Edo State:

1. that the use of instructional materials influences student’s understanding of the concept of cell biology.
2. that the use of instructional materials has no significant influence based on sex(either male or female).
3. that Government should provide good working Environment for teachers and necessary teaching equipment’s important for student to learn biology.
4. that teacher should recognize that Biological concepts can only be best taught to their learners via instructional materials.

Recommendation

From the founding and conclusion the following recommendations are made:

1. that Government should provide good working Environment in schools to foster better learning by students
2. that Government should employ more teachers who are technologically, and IT orientated.
3. that teaching and learning activities should be compactable to the student mind, age and psychological development..
4. and that school authorities allows students to learn basic biological concept at their best ways using very modern methods of teaching.

Suggestion for Further Research

Based on the conclusion and recommendations of the study the following are suggested for further studies:

- The present study assessed the influence of instructional materials on learning of Cell Biology in secondary schools in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area of Edo State.
- Further studies could be carried out on the knowledge, attitude and practice of the use of instructional material in Benin city metropolis

- Further studies could be could also focus on the on the need of instructional material in schools.

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APPENDIX A

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR BIOLOGY STUDENTS

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC DATA (PERSONAL DATA/BIODATA)

Please tick (✓) as appropriate on the spaces provided:

Sex: Male [] Female []

SECTION B

INSTRUCTION: Tick (✓) appropriate in the column provided against the option of your choice.

KEY TO SCORES

Strongly agree (SA)
Agree (A)
Disagree (D)
Strongly disagree (SD)

RQ1: What is the influence of instructional materials in the teaching and learning of Biology in secondary school?

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD
1	Students always have a better understanding of Cell Biology concepts anytime pictograms are used in the class				
2	I understand cell Biology very well when Charts are used in classroom				
3	I appreciate cell biology better when projector are used				
4	I find the Cell biology more interesting and understanding when Computer animations are used				
5	I like cell biology when Graphs are employed in learning				

6	Cell biology becomes interesting when Posters are used in the classroom				
7	I understand cell Biology concepts when models of plant cells are used				
8	I understand cell Biology concepts when models of animal cells are used				
9	I learn cell Biology better with digital computer simulators (DCS).				
10	I understand cell Biology better with use of Microscope				